

**KG Learn-Educational Kids Learning Game
(Android- Based)**

Bachelor of Science (Computer Science)

Session (2021-2025)

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KG Learn- Educational Kids Learning Game

Project

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&

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DEDICATION

First and foremost, we give our **deepest thanks to Allah Almighty**, whose boundless mercy, guidance, and blessings have enabled us to complete this project. It is by His will that we had the strength, patience, and determination to see this through. All praise and gratitude are due to Him alone.

We would also like to express our heartfelt appreciation to our families, friends, teachers, and everyone who supported and encouraged us along the way. Your unwavering belief in us has been a source of strength and motivation from the very beginning.

To our dear parents, thank you for your endless love, sacrifices, and support. We are truly grateful for everything you do, and we love you more than words can express.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS:

This research project was a collaborative effort between students of **Lahore College for Women University (LCWU)** and **National College of Business Administration & Economics (NCBA&E)**.

- **Noor Semab (LCWU):**
Contributed to the **problem analysis, data collection, class diagram and database design, back-end development, and testing of the system.**
- **Zain-UL-Abedin (NCBA&E):**
Responsible for the **literature review, system design, implementation of front-end modules, documentation, and final compilation of the thesis report.**

Both authors jointly contributed to the **idea formulation, research methodology, analysis, and final proofreading.** The project was completed through mutual cooperation and cross-institutional collaboration.

ABSTRACT

This proposal outlines the development of —Kg -learn|| an educational game designed for pre-school kids. Developed using Unity and C#, the game aims to enhance math skills through engaging and adaptive gameplay. **“Kg-Learn”** features exciting challenges, creative skills, discover fascinating facts and much more.

The game incorporates interactive quizzes, mini-games, all set within an adventurous storyline. With a focus on accessibility, the game will be available on multiple platforms, including PC, Android, and IOS. The project aims to create a fun and educational experience that supports children’s learning and development in a safe and engaging environment.

PREFACE

The basic purpose behind this section is to provide a quick description about the sections of this report. In this project we divided our documentation section into following SDLC (Software Development Life Cycle) phases:

- Project Management Plan
- Software Requirement Specification
- Software Design Specification
- Software Testing

Every phase has its own significance according to the “**KG Learn- Educational Kids Learning Game** “. This documentation facilitates those who want to know the development process, tools, methodologies and technicalities used in for the development of this application. We will follow SDLC (**i.e. agile model**) approach to complete this project.

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CHAPTER NO .1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Dive into a world of fun and learning with our kids' pre-school game project! Explore exciting challenges, creative skills, discover fascinating facts and much more. With engaging gameplay and educational content, it's the perfect adventure for young minds and it promotes active learning in early age. We will follow SDLC (i.e. **agile** model) approach to complete this project. At the end we will have a working product (i.e. Game).

The foundation of this project, is rooted in addressing the evolving landscape of education and technology. With the widespread integration of digital tools into children's lives, there exists a unique opportunity to harness the power of interactive games as educational tools. We try to combine entertainment and learning, recognizing that children engage more deeply with content when it's presented in a game.

Traditional educational methods often struggle to captivate the attention of young learners and fail to keep up with their evolving interests and needs. On the other hand, digital games have demonstrated the ability to engage and motivate children, providing a rich environment for learning through play. This project aims to build upon this potential by creating a simple yet impactful kids' learning application using modern game development techniques.

1.2 Motivation and Features

KG-Learn is an interactive educational game designed to engage and educate preschool-age children in a variety of fundamental skills essential for their development. The game combines playful activities, colorful visuals, and age-appropriate challenges to create an immersive learning experience. Thus motivation includes factors such as:

- Foster a love for learning by making education enjoyable and rewarding.
- Develop foundational skills in literacy, numeracy, and cognitive abilities.
- Encourage curiosity, exploration, and critical thinking.
- Support parents and caregivers in their efforts to facilitate their child's learning and development.
- Alphabet and Phonics recognition
- Numbers and Counting learning
- Colors and Shapes recognition
- Basic Vocabulary learning
- Fine Motor Skill development

1.3 Project Description

Kg-learn Educational Games are innovative educational tools designed to combine fun and learning, making the process of acquiring new knowledge and skills enjoyable for children. These games use interactive methods to teach essential skills.

1.4 Assumptions and Constraints

The game should work on IOS (I-phone and I-Pad), android devices (mobile phones and tabs) window (7, 8, 8.1, 10). The development platform only allows C-sharp scripts in the new version of unity, which is 2022.3.7f1. The game version is automatically updated. The limitations include custom physics due to unity engines built in physics APIs.

1.5 Problem Statement

Many children struggle with math, which is a fundamental skill critical for their academic success and future opportunities. Traditional teaching methods often fail to engage young learners effectively, making it challenging to maintain their interest and motivation. Additionally, there is a need for educational tools that are accessible, safe, and can adapt to individual learning paces.

Kg-learn address these challenges by providing an interactive and adaptive learning environment. The game's engaging storyline, varied math challenges, and supportive features like parental controls and customization ensure that children not only improve their math skills but also develop a positive attitude towards learning. By leveraging technology, "Kg-learn" aims to bridge the gap between education and entertainment, making learning an enjoyable experience for children.

1.6 Scope

The main purpose of this game —Kg-Learn is to developed a user-friendly environment in which user can easily avail his pleasure time. The project developed essential skills through interactive gameplay. A unique challenge to engage a player's mind. The project helps us to determine the difficulties which one does can be found in the production process and how to solve these problems.

1.7 Project Deliverable

The deliverable includes all documents, documentation, presentations and the final work software. Software project proposal, project documentation, user manual on the USB with the software resource file.

1.8 Audience and Reading Suggestions

This document intended for developers, tester and documentation writers. Developer should read each section to ensure understanding of this project. —Kg-learn is specifically designed for children aged 2-11. The game content is tailored to different age groups within this range, ensuring that younger children are introduced to basic concepts while older children tackle more complex problems. This product is continuation of an early game in the series known as —Splash Learn which provides a variety of interactive educational games tailored for Pre-K to Grade 5, covering subjects like math, reading, writing, calligraphy and many more.

1.9 Impact on Society:

This project aims to have a positive impact on society by:

- **Enhancing Education:** Providing an engaging and effective tool for children to improve their math skills, which are essential for their academic success and future opportunities.
- **Promoting Digital Literacy:** Encouraging children to interact with technology in a productive and educational manner.
- **Supporting Parents and Educators:** Offering a valuable resource for parents and educators to supplement traditional teaching methods and track children's progress.
- **Fostering a Love for Learning:** Making learning enjoyable and motivating children to develop a lifelong love for education.

1.10 Architectural Overview

In Kg Learn- Educational kids learning game will be developed using the Unity engine, providing a robust framework for creating 3D graphics and handling user interactions. UI and game elements will be designed to adapt to different screen sizes and resolutions, ensuring a consistent experience across all devices.

1.11 GHANTT-CHART (for Kg-Learn Educational Kids Learning Game)

Phase	Task	Duration	Start Date	End Date	Dependencies
Planning	Define scope & objectives	1 week	Sep 10-2024	Sep 17-2024	-
Planning	Market research	1 week	Sep 18-2024	Sep 25-2024	-
Planning	Educational content strategy	1 week	Sep 26-2024	Oct 3-2024	Define scope
Design	UI/UX Design	2 weeks	Oct 4-2024	Oct 18-2024	Planning phase
Design	Create characters & assets	2 weeks	Oct 19-2024	Nov 4-2024	Market research
Development	Build game engine & logic	3 weeks	Nov 5-2024	Nov 26-2024	Design phase
Development	Integrate educational modules	2 weeks	Nov 27-2024	Dec 11-2024	Content strategy
Development	Add sound & animations	1 week	Dec 12-2024	Dec 18-2024	Asset creation
Testing	Internal QA	1 week	Dec 19 -2024	Dec 27-2024	Development complete
Testing	Beta testing (with kids/parents)	1 week	Dec 28-2024	Jan 4-2025	Internal QA
Release	Final bug fixes & polish	1 week	Jan 5-2025	Jan 13-2025	Beta feedback
Release	Final submission	1 week	March 17-2025	March 23-2025	Publish

CHAPTER NO 2
PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN

2.1 Project Definition

It is most necessary to develop software project plan before moving towards SRS document so that we can work properly in flow within specific time. This part explains our project modeling Approach, Efforts Estimation, Risk identification and RMM plan, Requirements change management, Quality plan, software configuration plan, Resources plan (schedule Team member, Team structure, Roles and responsibilities) and infrastructure plan (development Environment, Test environment).

2.1.1- Modeling Approach

For develop any project the best way to follow a agile model so that we can follow easily and timely. This project that is —Kg Learn Educational Kids Learning Game using —unity software can be designed to develop according to agile model in this model next step is started when first step is completed. This is very easy and efficient model for kid’s educational learning application. In agile model steps are following:

2.1.2 Requirements and Analysis

In the Agile process, requirements are often captured as **user stories**, which are simple descriptions of a feature from the perspective of the end-user. These user stories are added to the **product backlog**, which is a prioritized list of work items that need to be done. This stage involves close collaboration with stakeholders to ensure that their needs and expectations are accurately understood and documented.

Figure 2.1 Agile Modology

2.1.3. Design

In the design phase, the team creates **design solutions** for the user stories planned for the sprint. This can involve creating wireframes, mockups, or detailed design documents, depending on the complexity of the feature. The goal is to have a clear design that guides the development process.

2.1.4 Coding

The development phase is where the actual **coding** takes place. Developers work on implementing the user stories, writing code, and creating unit tests to ensure the functionality works as expected. This phase involves close collaboration among team members, and progress is typically tracked in daily **stand-up meetings**, where each team member shares what they worked on, what they plan to work on, and any blockers they face.

2.1.5 Testing

Once the development of a feature is complete, it moves to the testing phase. Testers or developers perform various types of testing, including **unit testing**, **integration testing**, and **user acceptance testing (UAT)**, to ensure the feature works correctly and meets the requirements. Testing is a continuous process in Agile, often happening alongside development to catch issues early.

2.1.6. Deployment

If the completed work meets the required standards and has passed testing, it is deployed to production. This means the new features are made available to users. Deployment can happen at the end of each sprint or more frequently if the team uses a **continuous delivery** approach.

2.1.7. Maintenance

Once the product is live, the team continues to support and improve it based on user feedback and ongoing requirements. This may involve fixing bugs, enhancing existing features, or adding new features. The Agile process repeats, with each sprint building on the progress made in previous sprints.

2.2 External Milestone

Sir No	Milestone	Deliverable /Description/Comments	Date
01	Project proposal	The proposal defines the topics, establishes the scope required for completion times for each stage of work.	10- May-2024
02	Software Requirements Specifications (SRS)	This document contains requirements Specification and definition of the project software application	10- Sep-2024
03	Software project Management plan (PMP)	PMP defines whole planning about management of project.	18-Sep-2024
04	Software Design Specifications (SDS)	SDS describe the whole design the system by diagram.	4-Oct-2024 to 26-Nov-2024
05	Software Test specifications (STS)	Software Test document describe different types of testing adopted in project	19-Dec-2024
06	Project Evaluation & Documentation	Demonstrate code and documents of final project form internal presentation	20-May-2025
07	Evaluation	Demonstrate code documents final external presentation whole project code	20-may-2025

Table 2.1 External Milestone

2.2.1 Deliverable Artifacts

Here are following deliverable artifact:

- Requirements of function
- Requirements of non-function

- Use case
- Specifications of software Design
- Assumptions
- Constraints
- Test plan

2.2.2 Risk plans

There are few risks can occur in project:

- Risk of computer crash
- Risk of late delivery
- Technology does not meet specifications
- Risk change requirements

Sr no	Risk Description	Probability	Mitigation plan	Monitoring	Management
01	Tools are not appropriate	High	It can be mitigated by using appropriate tools for developing project.	By comparing different tools	Suggest best tools
02	If meeting does not conduct regularly, it will affect the working of project	High	Meeting must be conduct regularly	Each number must be assigning task	Task must be complete before given time
03	Computer crash	High	It can be mitigate by doing back up date	Backup copies should place location	Back up should done
04	Computer crash	High	It can be mitigated by doing back up date	Backup copies should place location	Back up should done immediately

Table 2.2 RMMM Plan

2.3 Quality Assurance

Quality assurance auditing is a concept widely used internal, external, and customer audits measuring quality. The challenge correctly development research cycles any manufacturing products results forms. It also important regularly quality procedure efficiency procedure

- Plans: what are planning? (Future)
- Progress: what have you done? (Past)
- Problems: what problem are you facing? (Present)

This simplest status reporting system is called PPP – plans, progress, and problems.

2.4 Communication Plan

A communication plan is providing specific information delivered management. Communication plans play an important role change management. Method offers opportunity for people ask questions providing feedback real value project.

- Meeting summaries
- Status report
- Newsletter
- Survey

2.5 Test Case

Test case discussed documents.

2.6 Software Configuration Plan

Our software configuration management plan. The simple flow plan identification any type change occurs project. After few steps roughly list software configuration module basic unit of modification (e.g. design documents, code of any module, test plan etc.)

2.7 Resource Plan

Summarizes the level of resource needed complete project. A document specifies complete project. Project resources Management will need create comprehensive Resources plan, identified. By implementation proper Resources planning practice, it also helps you with budgeting and forecasting project.

2.7.1 Effort Estimation

Work breaks down structure	Resources	Days
Requirement gathering	4	6
Analysis	2	2
Project proposal	1	12
Review	2	2
software requirement specification	2	10
Review	1	3
Use case model	2	6
Coding review	2	30
Test plan	2	20
Review	4	8
Deploy	4	4

Table 2.3: Project Effort Estimation

2.7.2 Schedule

Throughout the project weekly meeting held internal advisor and project coordinator.

2.7.3 Team Member

Our projects team compromise two members;

- One member designed for software development and documentation.
- Second member act as internal project coordinator.

2.8 Infrastructure Plan

Infrastructure explained below.

2.8.1 Development Environment

The development environment consist two parts

- Development machine
- Development tools

2.8.2 Development Machine

The tools required development machine application are:

- Android Game
- Internet connection
- Min 60 GB

2.8.3 Development Tools

Development Tools used in —Kg Learn- Educational Kids learning game" is discussed below:

Documentation:

- Microsoft office 2021
- Microsoft VISIO Coding: Visual studio 2021

Test Environment:

Test Environment some hardware specifications that is listed below:

- Hardware specifications: 2GB RAM
- Hardware specifications 50-60mbs

Development Tools:

- Unity 2022.3.7f1 (game engine)
 - <Android sdk / Android jdk>
- (Build tool in unity to convert unity(file) into apk.)

- Visual studio (C# language is used for scripting in VS)
- Unity edits
- Pixabay (sounds)
- Canva (art/animation)

CHAPTER NO 3
SOFTWARE DESIGN SPECIFICATIONS

3.1 Design Model

This chapter elaborates the design goals and architecture of the underlying project along with the type of methodology. There is no separate view defined. All views are constructed based on the UML (Unified Modeling Language) and are developed in Microsoft Visio and star UML.

3.1.1 Methodology

This game uses the most famous methodology "agile Model". The purpose of adopting this model is evident, given its benefits in iterative development and flexibility. The project aims to be compatible with all possible devices. Prior to the actual development, multiple prototypes were created to refine the functionalities of the project. These prototypes were regularly reviewed and discussed with relevant stakeholders.

3.2 Design and Description

3.2.1 Use cases Diagram

A **use case diagram** is a type of UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagram that represents the **functional requirements** of a system. It shows the interactions between **actors** (users or other systems) and the **use cases** (functions or services the system provides).

Use case diagrams help in understanding **what the system should do** from the user's perspective. They include elements like:

- **Actors:** External entities (e.g., users or other systems) that interact with the system.
- **Use Cases:** Specific functions or actions the system performs.
- **Relationships:** Such as **include**, **extend**, and **association** to show how use cases are connected or dependent.

These diagrams are widely used during the **requirement gathering and analysis** phase to ensure that all stakeholders have a clear understanding of the system's functionality.

Use case diagrams are used to describe functional requirements of the system. The diagrams are drawn below.

Figure 3.1 Shows the Use Case diagram for “**Kg Learn- Educational Kids Learning Game**”

Figure 3.1 use case diagram

3.2.2 Use Case Specification

Use Case 1: Start Game

Description:

This use case is the entry point for the player, allowing them to launch the game from the main menu. It initiates the game engine and prepares the interface for interaction. This step is critical as it sets the tone for the entire user experience. A seamless start encourages player engagement and reduces friction in accessing educational content.

This use case includes initializing necessary game assets, displaying loading screens, and directing the user to the interactive learning interface. For young children, an intuitive and quick start boosts confidence and ensures they can begin playing with minimal assistance.

UC-01	Start Game
Action	Player
Use case ID	UC-01
Pre-Condition	Game should be installed and running
Game scenario	Player will play the game Player will quit the game anytime
Exception	Player will not satisfy by the game due to some reasons.

Table 3.1 use case start game

Figure 3.1.a use case 1

Use Case 2: Select Category

Description:

This use case enables players—particularly children—to choose from a variety of educational content categories presented on the main menu. Each category is designed with specific learning objectives and interactive content, catering to early learners. Categories may include **Alphabet Tracing**, **Number Tracing**, **Alphabet Recognition**, **Animals Recognition** and more.

By allowing players to select a category, the game provides a personalized experience, encouraging exploration and engagement across multiple learning areas. For example, **Alphabet Tracing** promotes fine motor skills and letter formation, while **Animals** may teach names, sounds, and visual recognition.

UC-02	Select Category
Actor	Player
Use case ID	UC- 02
Pre-conditions	Game will be in running phase
Main scenario	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go to the main menu • go the start button • Tap on the level button to level on game
Post-conditions	Player will choose the game
Exceptions	Player may not be satisfied by the game due to some Reasons

Table 3.2 use case select different category

Figure 3.1.b use case 2

Use Case 3: Practice Writing

Description:

This use case allows children to **practice writing letters, numbers, or shapes** using interactive tracing tools within the game. The goal is to help young learners develop **fine motor skills, hand-eye coordination, and early writing abilities** through guided visual and audio feedback.

The writing screen typically displays a dotted outline of a letter or number, along with instructions or prompts. As the child traces over the shape using touch input, the system provides instant feedback—encouraging proper stroke order and precision.

UC-03	Practice Writing
Actor	Player
Use case ID	UC-03
Pre-condition	Game will be start
Main scenario	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Click the plat button Game will be start
Post condition	Game will be start again
Exception	Player will not be satisfied by the game due to some Reasons

Table 3.3 use case Practice Writing

Figure 3.1.c use case 3

Use Case 4: Play Quiz

Description:

This use case allows the player to engage in an interactive **quiz session** designed to assess their understanding of previously learned content. The quiz presents a variety of question types—such as **multiple choice, matching, or true/false**—based on topics like **alphabets, numbers, shapes, animals, and more**.

The purpose of the quiz is to **reinforce learning**, encourage **active recall**, and provide **feedback** on the child’s progress. The game keeps the experience fun and motivating by rewarding correct answers with stars, animations, or sounds.

UC-04	Play Quiz
Actor	Player
Use case ID	UC-04
Pre-condition	The player must have selected a category
Main scenario	The player played the game and earn the score (points)
Post condition	Game will be start again
Exception	Player will not be satisfied by the game due to some reasons

Table 3.4 use case Play Quiz

Figure 3.1.d use case 4

Use Case 5: Adjust Setting

Description:

The **Settings** feature allows users—especially parents or guardians—to customize the game environment based on the child’s needs and preferences. It includes options to adjust **sound/music volume**, toggle **voice instructions**, change **language settings**, set **difficulty level**, enable or disable **background music**.

UC-05	Setting
Actor	Player, parents
Use case ID	UC-05
Pre-conditions	The game must be running.
Main scenario	Parents and Player can adjust the settings
Post conditions	The player or parent must access the main menu.
Exceptions	Player will not be satisfied by the game due to some reasons

Table 3.5 use case Adjust Setting

Figure 3.1.e use case 5

Use Case 6: Monitor Safe Usage

Description:

This use case enables parents to observe their child's activity within the app. It ensures that children use the game in a secure, educationally appropriate manner, promoting responsible screen time and safety in digital learning.

UC-06	Monitor Safe Usage
Actor	Parent
Use case ID	UC-06
Pre-condition	Parent can monitor their child for safety purpose
Main scenario	Parents monitor their child
Post conditions	Parents will monitor their children for safe usage and check the scores.
Exceptions	Player will not be satisfied by the game due to some reasons

Table 3.6 use case monitor safe usage

Figure 3.1.f use case 6

Use Case 7: Exit the Game

Description:

This use case describes the procedure for safely exiting the game. It ensures that any ongoing progress is saved and that the game shuts down in an orderly manner. For younger users, a clear and easy exit pathway prevents confusion and reinforces structured playtime. For parents, it reassures that the session is ending appropriately and that their child is not lingering in the app unsupervised. This functionality also prevents loss of data and ensures that user preferences are retained for future sessions.

UC-06	Exit Game
Actor	System
Use case ID	UC-08
Pre-condition	Player can exit the game
Main scenario	Click on exit game
Post conditions	The game will be exit by using exit button
Exceptions	Player will not be satisfied by the game due to some reasons

Table 3.7 use case exit game

Figure 3.1.g use case 7

3.2.3 Flow Diagram

A **flow diagram** is a graphical representation that illustrates the sequence of steps, decisions, and processes involved in a particular system, task, or operation. It uses standardized symbols such as arrows, rectangles, diamonds, and ovals to show the **flow of control** or **data** from one point to another.

Flow diagrams are widely used in various fields such as **computer science, engineering, business, and project management** to help understand, analyze, and communicate how processes work. They are especially helpful in identifying bottlenecks, redundancies, and areas for improvement.

Figure 3.3 Flow Diagram

3.2.4 Activity Diagram

An **activity diagram** is a type of UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagram that visually represents the flow of activities or actions in a system or process. It shows the sequence of steps, decisions, parallel processes, and the start and end points. Activity diagrams are commonly used to model business workflows or the logic of complex operations in software systems.

Fig 3.4 Activity Diagram

3.2.5 State Diagram

A **state diagram** is a UML diagram that shows how an object changes its state in response to events over time. It represents different states of an object, the transitions between those states, and the events that trigger those transitions. State diagrams are useful for modeling the behavior of systems, especially those with complex state-dependent logic.

Fig 3.5 State Diagram

3.2.6 Class Diagram

A **class diagram** is a UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagram that shows the structure of a system by representing its **classes**, **attributes**, **methods**, and the **relationships** between classes. It is commonly used in object-oriented design to model the static structure of software systems and to illustrate how different classes interact with each other.

The class diagram provides a structural overview of the core components involved in the **Educational Kids Learning Game**. It models the **static relationships** between classes, their **attributes**, **methods**, and **associations**, effectively outlining how different parts of the system interact with one another. This diagram supports object-oriented design principles and guides the development process.

Each class is depicted as a box divided into three sections:

1. **Class Name**
2. **Attributes (variables or properties)**
3. **Methods (operations or functions)**

Purpose of this Diagram

This class diagram clearly outlines the architecture of the game, supporting modular development, maintainability, and future scalability. It reflects **object-oriented principles**, such as **encapsulation**, **abstraction**, and **modular design**, making it easier for developers and stakeholders to understand the system's structure and behavior.

Fig 3.6 Class Diagram

CHAPTER NO 4
SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

4.1 Purpose of the Document

This document serves as a complete description of the behavior of **Kg Learn- Educational kids learning game**. Its use to list out its functions, Adaptive learning, Comprehensive skills, Engaging gameplay, multi-platform accessibility, Safe learning environment. It's an interactive game. It's use to list out its functions, its target user base, its operating environment, and its various requirements and so on. It is also including a set of use cases that describe interactions of the users with the system. It is an interactive game with a textual interface. The purpose of this document is to gather and analyze and give an in-depth insight of the Kg Learn- Educational Kids Learning Game.

4.2 Functional Requirements

This file serves as a complete description of the behavior of Kg Learn- Educational Kids Learning Game. So, the motive of this file is to listing all its capabilities and functions, its intended user base, its running environment and its various requirements etc. It also carries a sequence of use cases describing user interactions with the system. It is an interactive game with a text-based interface. The motive of this document is to accumulate, examine and provide a thoroughly look at the 3-D Learning Game.

4.2.1 Product Functions

The product functions are the prior requirements which might to be necessarily fulfilled earlier than the product delivery. Kg Learn-Educational Kids Learning Game is divided into three main functions. The totally Physics based functionalities, the level and other Functionalities and user interface Functionalities.

Main Menu Functions

- **Start Game ()** - Initializes the game environment and loads the main menu.
- **Load subject ()** - Loads a specific level or stage based on the player's progress.
- **Generate Challenge (level, skill Type)** - Generates math problems (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division) based on the player's level and selected skill type.
- **Check Answer (player Answer, correct Answer)** - Compares the player's answer with the correct answer and returns the result.
- **Provide Feedback (is Correct)** - Provides immediate feedback based on whether the player's answer is correct or incorrect.

- **Track Progress (player ID)** - Tracks the player's progress and stores their performance data.
- **Update Skill Level (player ID, new Skill Level)** - Updates the player's skill level based on their progress and performance.

Mini-Game Functions

- **Start Mini game (mini-Game Type)** - Initiates a specific mini-game based on the selected type.
- **Complete Mini-game (player-ID, mini-Game Result)**- Records the player's performance in the mini-game and awards points or rewards

Utility Functions

- **Save Game (player ID)** - Saves the current game state and player progress.
- **Load Game (player ID)** - Loads the saved game state and player progress.
- **Exit Game ()** - Exits the game and returns to the main menu.

4.2.2 User Classes and Characteristics

The game must be usable by any user. No special know-how or abilities are required. User is not anticipated to analyze with a purpose to start the usage of the game.

4.2.3 Operating Environment

The Environment for the effective use of this project includes platforms such as:

- IOS Devices
- Android Devices
- Mac OSX

4.3 Design and Implementation Constraints

The whole game on art side is designed with photo-shop and practical lighting fixtures procedurally with clean anti-aliasing rendering to make fun and interactive.

4.3.1 Design Constraints

1. **Age-Appropriate Content:** The game's content, challenges, and interface must be suitable for children aged 4-12. This includes using simple language, appropriate difficulty levels, and engaging visuals.

2. **User Interface (UI):** The UI must be intuitive and easy to navigate for young children. This includes large buttons, clear instructions, and minimal text.
3. **Visual and Audio Elements:**
 - High-quality 3D graphics and animations that is engaging and visually appealing to children.
 - Age-appropriate sound effects and background music that enhance the gameplay experience without being distracting.
4. **Accessibility:**
 - The game must be accessible on multiple platforms (PC, Android, and IOS) and provide support for various screen sizes and resolutions.
 - Include features like adjustable text sizes and color contrast settings to accommodate children with visual impairments.
5. **Parental Controls:** The game must include robust parental control features allowing parents to monitor their child's progress, set usage limits, and adjust difficulty settings.

4.3.2 Implementation Constraints

1. **Technology Stack:** The game will be developed using Unity as the primary game engine and C# as the programming language.
2. **Platform Compatibility:** The game must be compatible with PC, Android, and IOS platforms. This requires ensuring that the codebase is optimized for cross-platform deployment.
3. **Data Security:** The game must ensure the security of user data, including personal information and progress data. This involves implementing secure authentication methods and data encryption.
4. **Performance:** The game must run smoothly on a range of devices, including lower-end smartphones and tablets. This requires optimizing graphics and animations to maintain performance without compromising quality.
5. **Resource Allocation:** The development team must include Unity developers, graphic designers, and educational consultants. The project timeline must be managed to ensure that each phase is completed within the estimated 4-12 months.

4.4 Assumptions and Limitations

4.4.1 Assumptions

- Children aged 4-12 will find the game engaging and be motivated to improve their math skills through gameplay.
- The game will run smoothly on the specified platforms (PC, Android, iOS) without significant performance issues.
- The majority of the target users will have access to devices that can run the game (PC, smartphones, tablets).
- Parents will actively use the parental control features to monitor and support their child's learning
- The challenges and educational content are effective in enhancing children's skills.
- There is a market demand for educational games that combine learning and fun for children.

4.4.2 Limitations

- Lower-end devices may experience performance issues, such as lag or slower loading times, which could affect the user experience.
- Some game features, such as progress tracking and updates, may require an internet connection, limiting accessibility for users with poor connectivity.
- Adapting educational content to suit a wide age range (4-12) may be challenging, as younger and older children have different learning needs and attention spans.
- The estimated timeline of 6-12 months may be optimistic, and unforeseen challenges could extend the development period.
- Budget limitations might affect the quality of graphics, animations, and additional features that could enhance the game.
- The game's content may need to be adjusted to accommodate cultural differences and educational standards in various regions.
- Gathering and implementing feedback from diverse user groups may be time-consuming and resource-intensive.

- Ensuring compliance with varying child protection laws and privacy regulations across different regions can be complex and may require ongoing adjustments.

4.5 User Documentation

There might be a basic How- to -guide packaged with a support aid user.

4.6 External Interface Requirements

4.6.1. Hardware Interfaces

There are almost 6-7 hardware interfaces for us to interact with those are:

1. Keyboard
2. Mouse
3. MAC
4. iPhone Devices.
5. Android Devices

All these are handled by the C-sharp classes and will mostly be simple for us to interact with. The program requires rather modest hardware to run on.

4.6.1.2 PC Requirements

- Core i5
 - **Operating System:** Win 10
 - **RAM:** 2 to 4 GB maximum

4.6.1.2 IOS Devices

iPhone 4s or Higher with 8 GB memory

4.6.1.3 Android Devices

Android version 6+ marshmallow and above or 500Mb ram.

4.6.2 Software Interfaces

There are many interfaces using and there are many software interfaces we are using here.

- For development purposes we are using: 3d Engine Version 2022.3.7f1
- For testing purposes, we are using different interfaces like:
 - Unity remote to test on android and iOS devices
 - iPhone/iPad C-sharp as a coding(scripting) Language

4.7 System Feature's

Description and Priority	The user must be able to start the game from the game's executable file or from the file installed from the selected hardware.
Stimulus/response sequences	The response/stimulus for different user classes are: Tap the Kg learn game app icon on any touchscreen device. Double clicks the app icon on PC and Mac devices
Functional requirements REQ-1	The Kg Learn game must be installed or copied on the device on which we want to play or perform. Output: the player begins to run.
Pre-condition	The Kg Learn game must be properly installed or copied to the device, and the device must be powered on with sufficient resources (e.g., memory and processing power) to run the application.
Post condition	The Kg Learn game successfully launches, displaying the main menu or starting screen, ready for user interaction.

Table 4.1 Start Game

Description and Priority	The "Play" button on the main menu page allows users to start a new game session
Stimulus/response sequences	<p>User clicks on the "Play" button.</p> <p>Response:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The game initializes a new session. 2. The game transitions from the main menu to the game play interface. 3. Any necessary loading screens or animations are displayed during the transition. 4. Background music and sound effects for the game start playing. 5. User's selected preferences or saved settings are applied to the new game session.
Functional Requirements REQ-1.	<p>FR-1.1: The game should save any ongoing game progress if a previous session is active.</p> <p>FR-1.2: The game should load the necessary assets and data for a new game session.</p> <p>FR-1.3: The game should apply user preferences and settings to the new game session.</p> <p>FR-1.4: The game should display a loading screen or animation during the transition.</p> <p>FR-1.5: The game should start background music and sound effects upon entering the game play interface.</p> <p>FR-1.6: The game should present the user with options for various educational activities (poems, number tracing, number recognition, alphabet tracing, alphabet recognition, months, days, fruits, animals, and mini-games).</p>
Post-Condition	The game play interface is loaded, and the user is able to interact with the game.
Pre-Condition	The main menu page is loaded, and the "Play" button is visible and clickable.

Table 4.2 Play Button

Description and Priority	The volume button allows users to control the game's audio settings, including background music and sound effects.
Stimulus/response sequences	User interacts with the volume button.
Functional Requirements REQ-2	When the user interacts with the volume button, the game should display a volume control interface and allow the user to adjust audio settings.
Preconditions	The game play page is loaded, and the volume button is visible and clickable.
Post conditions	The audio settings are adjusted as per the user's preferences, and the changes are saved.

Table 4.3 Volume Button

Description and Priority	User can choose between various educational activities, including number, number writing, alphabet, alphabet writing, poems, animals, fruits, months, days and mini game.
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Stimulus/response sequences	<p>Stimulus: User selects a category from the available options. Response:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The game displays a list of categories: number, number writing, alphabet, alphabet writing, poems, animals, fruits, months, days and mini game. 2. The user clicks on one of the categories. 3. The game transitions to the selected activity page. 4. Any necessary loading screens or animations are displayed during the transition. 5. The game applies the user's selected preferences or saved settings to the new activity session. 6. The activity begins, and the user can start interacting with it.
Functional Requirements REQ-3.	<p>FR-3.1: The game should display a list of categories: poems, number tracing, number recognition, alphabet tracing, alphabet recognition, months, days, fruits, animals, and mini-games.</p> <p>FR-3.2: The game should allow the user to select a category by clicking on it.</p> <p>FR-3.3: The game should transition to the selected activity page after a category is selected.</p> <p>FR-3.4: The game should display a loading screen or animation during the transition.</p> <p>FR-3.5: The game should apply user preferences and settings to the new activity session.</p> <p>FR-3.6: The game should start the selected activity and allow the user to interact with it.</p>
Preconditions	The category selection page is loaded, and the categories are visible and clickable.
Post conditions	The selected activity page is loaded, and the user can interact with the activity.

Table 4.4 Main Menu

Description and Priority	The back button allows users to navigate back to the category selection page from any selected activity page.
Stimulus/response sequences	<p>User clicks on the back button.</p> <p>Response:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user clicks on the back button while on any activity page. 2. The game transitions back to the category selection page. 3. Any necessary loading screens or animations are displayed during the transition. 4. The user can select another category or activity from the category selection page.
Functional Requirements REQ-4.	<p>FR-4.1: The game should display a back button on each activity page.</p> <p>FR-4.2: The game should allow the user to click the back button to navigate back to the category selection page.</p> <p>FR-4.3: The game should transition back to the category selection page after the back button is clicked.</p> <p>FR-4.4: The game should display a loading screen or animation during the transition.</p> <p>FR-4.5: The game should retain the user's previous selections and preferences when navigating back to the category selection page.</p>
Preconditions	The user is on any activity page, and the back button is visible and clickable.
Post conditions	The category selection page is loaded, and the user can select another category or activity.

Table 4.5 Back Button

Description and Priority	When the user clicks the left or right button, the game should navigate to the previous or next category or activity page.
Stimulus/response sequences	<p>Stimulus: User clicks on the left or right button.</p> <p>Response:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user clicks on the left or right button on any category page. 2. The game transitions to the previous or next category or activity page. 3. Any necessary loading screens or animations are displayed during the transition. 4. The user can interact with the new category or activity.
Functional Requirements REQ-5.	<p>FR-5.1: The game should display left and right buttons on each category or activity page.</p> <p>FR-5.2: The game should allow the user to click the left or right button to navigate to the previous or next category or activity page.</p>
Preconditions	The user is on any category or activity page, and the left and right buttons are visible and clickable
Post conditions	The previous or next category or activity page is loaded, and the user can interact with the new page.

Table 4.6 Left and Right Button

Description and Priority	The user can play the mini games by clicking on the play button on the main menu page
Stimulus/response sequences	User: click the play button on the main menu screen
Functional Requirements REQ-6.	The user has quiz options including: Math's, English and both. The player presses the button the play the quiz
Pre-condition	The user has access to the game's settings or the main menu where the "Quit Game" button is available
Post condition	The user is returned to the main menu or exits the game application entirely.

Table 4.7 Play Button

Description and Priority	The user can quit from settings options using quit button.
Stimulus/response sequences	User: click the exit button on the setting option.
Functional Requirements REQ-7.	User on setting screen output: quit game
Pre-condition	The user has successfully launched the game application.
Post condition	The user is navigated from the main menu to the activity selection screen.

Table 4.8 Quit Game

Description and Priority	User can pause the game and also resume the game by using pause button
Stimulus/response sequences	User: click the pause button
Functional Requirements REQ-8.	The —resume option must continue the game without any change of state of the level for the moment of the pause action <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The player presses the pause button on the gameplay interface.
Pre-condition	The game is currently running and active.
Post condition	The game is successfully paused.

Table 4.9 Pause Game

4.8 Non-Functional Requirements

4.8.1 Performance Requirements

The game must be able to run at 30 FPS (frames per second) on whatever platform we implement on it. This game may fall on lower spec devices. It is recommended to use the high space device to take advantage of and get around 60 frames per second.

- **Response Time:** The game should have minimal lag, with response times for user actions not exceeding 1 second.
- **Load Time:** Initial game load time should be under 5 seconds on average devices. Level load times should be under 3 seconds.

4.8.2 Security Requirements

Security will not be a concern for this project, as no sensitive data is stored. However, distribution and copyright are reserved only to the development and publishing team.

- **Data Privacy:** Ensure all user data is securely stored and comply with data protection regulations such as COPPA.
- **User Authentication:** Implement secure authentication methods to protect user accounts and progress data.
- **Encryption:** Use encryption protocols (e.g., SSL/TLS) for data transmission between the client and server.

4.8.3 Usability

The scope of the product is extensive. People of all ages can play without any effort.

- **Ease of Use:** The game should be intuitive and easy for children aged 4-12 to navigate without adult assistance.
- **Accessibility:** Include adjustable text sizes, color contrast options, and audio controls to accommodate children with visual or hearing impairments.
- **Help and Tutorials:** Provide clear instructions, tutorials, and help options accessible from the main menu

4.8.4 Availability

This game will be available unless it is removed from the mobile market. Distribution and copyright are reserved only to the development and publishing team.

4.8.5 Portability

The game requires minimum effort in terms of installation. Also, it should work on any smart mobile devices and windows or mac.

4.8.6 Software Quality Attribute

This game offers a nice and easy to use graphical interface with relatively simple functions. Any player should be able to play the game without any specific knowledge or experience. Users only have to perform certain actions and with a few clicks they can perform the desired action.

4.8.7 Privacy

- **User Data Collection:** Minimize the collection of personal data to only what is necessary for the game's functionality.

- **User Consent:** Obtain explicit consent from parents or guardians before collecting any personal data from children.
- **Data Anonymization:** Anonymize user data where possible to protect the identities of children.
- **Privacy Policy:** Provide a clear and accessible privacy policy that outlines how user data is collected, used, and protected.

Information of the user must be private in this game and no personal data will be encrypted.

CHAPTER NO 5
IMPLEMENTATION AND EVALUATION

5.1 Introduction

The main purpose of plan for the Kg Learn-Educational Kids Learning Game discusses in Testing use case it. The software project test plan describes the objective software testing responsible specific risks association test plan.

5.2 Features and Task Completed

1. Letter of Alphabets Recognition

- Interactive alphabet learning activities.
- Animated characters representing each letter.
- Voice narration for each letter to aid recognition.

2. Numbers Learning/Recognition

- Visual representation of numbers with colorful graphics.
- Voice narration for numbers from 1 to 10.

3. Numbers Tracing

- Guided tracing activities for numbers.
- Progressive difficulty levels, starting with simple numbers and progressing to more complex ones.
- Feedback on tracing accuracy, such as visual cues or audio prompts.
- Reward system for completing tracing tasks successfully.

4. Alphabets Tracing

- Similar to numbers tracing but for alphabets.
- Guided tracing with arrows or outlines to assist kids.
- Progressive difficulty levels, starting with simple letters and progressing to more complex ones.

- Reinforcement of correct tracing strokes through visual and audio feedback.

5. Animal Names

- Picture of animals where kids learn their names.
- Animal sounds to make learning more engaging.
- Quiz mode where kids can identify animals based on pictures or descriptions.

6. Fruits Names

- Similar features to the animal names module but focused on fruits.
- Interactive fruit-themed activities, such as sorting or matching games.
- Voice narration for fruit names.
- Virtual fruit market or garden where kids can learn about different fruits.

7. Months Names

- Interface with visuals representing each month.
- Voice narration for month names.

8. Names of Days

- Interactive interface displaying the days of the week.
- Voice narration for days of the week.

9. Poems

- Collection of nursery rhymes and children's poems.
- Karaoke-style sing-along mode with highlighted lyrics.

10. Quiz

- Multiple-choice or matching quizzes on various topics covered in the game.
- Progress tracking to monitor kids' performance and improvement.

5.3 Purpose of testing:

The purpose of test plan is to achieve the following

- Define the activities required to conduct unit, integration, system and acceptance testing

- Communicate to all team members the various dependencies and risks.

5.4 Objectives

The main objectives of the test plan for the Kg-Learn Educational Kids Learning Game are as follows:

- To identify the features of the App, that will be tested.
- To identify and define all the activities necessary to prepare for and conduct the testing.
- Process on android application.
- To define the pass/ fail criteria for each item that will be tested.
- To identify the deliverable of the testing phase.
- To define any suspension criteria and resumption technique.
- To discuss the testing techniques being used to test game

5.5 Testing Cases

Test case 1	Test case of game start
Screen name	Kg learn
Test case ID	TC:01
Application Name	Kg Learn
Purpose	To initiate the application
Scenario	Start game while opening multiple app
Environment	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	None
Strategy	Click on game app
Expected result	Game should start
Result	Game started

Table 5.5.1: Test case 1: Testing the game play

Test case 2	Test case of play button
Screen name	Kg learn
Test case ID	TC:02
Application Name	Kg learn
Purpose	To initiate the application to start interface
Scenario	Main has different options/ categories.
Environment	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	None
Strategy	Click play, setting and categories new screen appeared
Result	Main screen has no bug

Table 5.5.2: Test case 2: Testing the main menu page

Test case 3	Test case of the play button
Screen name	Kg Learn
Test case ID	TC: 03
Application Name	Kg learn
Purpose	To get input from the user
Scenario	Select environment
Environment	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	Main screen appeared
Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Click any environment • User will play the game
Expected result	By clicking environment new screen appeared
Result	Main screen has no bugs

Table 5.5.3: Test Case 3: Testing Play Button

Test case 4	Test case of the quit game
Screen name	Kg learn
Test case ID	TC:04
Application Name	Kg Learn
Purpose	Game end
Scenario	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	Main screen appeared
Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Get score • Complete stage • End game appeared
Expected result	By clicking end game screen will be shown
Result	Main screen has no bugs

Table 5.5.4: Case 4: Testing the Quit Button

Test case 5	Test case of setting
Screen name	Kg learn
Test case ID	TC:05
Application Name	Kg Learn
Purpose	Show screen
Environment	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	Main screen appeared
Strategy	Screen will be appeared where you can set the volume and brightness of the game
Expected result	By clicking setting screen will be shown
Result	Main screen has no bugs

Table 5.5.5: Test Case 5: Testing Setting Button

Test case 6	To check the working of each categories according to the scenario
Screen name	Kg learn
Test case ID	TC:06
Application Name	Kg Learn
Purpose	Show different categories
Environment	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	Main screen appeared
Strategy	Check the categories
Expected result	By clicking on different categories the new screen will be shown
Result	Screen has no bugs

Table 5.5.6: Test Case 6: Check the Different Categories on the Main Menu

Test case 7	To check the battery performance
Screen name	Kg learn
Test case ID	TC:07
Application Name	Kg learn
Purpose	Battery life estimation
Environment	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	None
Strategy	None
Expected result	Score should be saved
Result	Score not saved

Table 5.5.7: Test Case 7; Check the Battery Effect if the Phone Gets off Whether the Screen will Save or Not

Test case 7	To check the pause effect
Screen name	Kg learn
Test case ID	TC:08
Application Name	Kg learn
Purpose	Check pause functionality
Environment	Unity 3D
Pre-requistic	None
Strategy	None
Expected result	The game should be paused
Result	The game has been paused

Table 5.5.8: Test Case 8: Check if the Game is Paused when Call received or Sleep Mode

Graphic user interface

UI-01	
Interface ID	UI-01
Description	Central screen where players access all game features and categories.

UI-01: Main Menu Interface

<p style="text-align: center;">UI-02</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Interface ID</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">UI-02</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Description</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select the different categories • Displays learning topics like numbers, alphabets, and animals for selection.

UI-02: Different Categories Interface

UI-03	
Interface ID	UI-03
Description	The number recognition interface

UI-03: Numbers Interface

UI-04	
Interface ID	UI-04
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Writing / calligraphy interface• Enables tracing of letters and numbers to develop motor and writing skills.

UI-04: Writing Interface

UI-05	
Interface ID	UI-05
Description	Alphabet recognition, shapes, numbers and lines categories appear on the screen

UI-05: Alphabet Interface

UI-06	
Interface ID	UI-06
Description	Different poems videos will show on the screen

UI-06: Poem Interface

UI-07	
Interface ID	UI-07
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Animal recognition interface• Displays animals with names and sounds to enhance vocabulary.

UI-07: Animal Interface

UI-08	
Interface ID	UI-08
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Fruit recognition interface• Helps children learn fruit names through pictures and audio.

UI-08: Fruits Interface

UI-09	
Interface ID	UI-09
Description	Teaches month names with visual and audio reinforcement.

UI-09: Months Interface

UI-10	
Interface ID	UI-10
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Select the different categories• Presents days of the week with supportive visuals and sound.

UI-10: Days Interface

UI-11	
Interface ID	UI-11
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Quiz option will appear on screen• Provides quizzes to assess and reinforce learning progress.

UI-11: Play Interface (Quiz)

UI-12	
Interface ID	UI-12
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting option will appear on the screen • Allows users to control audio, brightness, and parental settings.

UI-12: Setting Interface

5.6 Project – Initialization -Setup-

Before start building, we will get a well-equipped development environment and meet the **minimum system requirements** for this game development project, allowing you to work efficiently. Here's a guide to setting up your development environment and the minimum system requirements:

- **Processor:** Quad-core CPU or better
- **Memory:** 8 GB RAM or more
- **Graphics Card:** DirectX 11 or later compatible GPU with 2 GB VRAM or more
- **Storage:** SSD recommended for faster loading times
- **Display:** 1920x1080 resolution or higher
- **Operating System:** Windows 7 SP1+, macOS 10.12+, or Ubuntu 16.04+

5.6.1 To initialize this project and set up the required tools, follow these steps:

1. **Download and Install Unity Hub:** Unity Hub is a management tool that allows you to easily install and manage different versions of Unity. You can download it from the official Unity website: [UNITY download link](#)
2. **Install Unity:** Once Unity Hub is installed, open it and navigate to the "Installs" tab. Click on the "Add" button to select the version of Unity you want to use for your project. For a new project, it's recommended to use the latest stable version available. After selecting the version, click "Next" and follow the installation prompts.
3. **Create a New Unity Project:** Open Unity Hub and navigate to the "Projects" tab. Click on the "New" button, then choose a template. Since this is a kids' game, you might want to start with the "2D mobile" template depending on your game's requirements. Give your project a name such as "KG Learn (Kids Game Learn)" and specify a location to save it.
4. **Install Visual Studio or Visual Studio Code:** Unity supports both Visual Studio and Visual Studio Code for scripting to game on C# language. You can download and install either of them based on your preference.
 - Visual Studio: [Download Visual Studio](#)
 - Visual Studio Code: [Download Visual Studio Code](#)

5. **Configure Unity Preferences:** Inside Unity, go to "Edit" → "Preferences" (Windows) or "Unity" → "Preferences" (Mac). Set up your preferences including external script editor (if you installed Visual Studio or Visual Studio Code), layout preferences, etc.
6. **Install Required Packages/Add-ons:** Depending on the specific requirements of your project, you might need to install additional packages or add-ons from the Unity Asset Store. For this game, you may want to look for appropriate assets such as graphics, sounds, and plugins to enhance your game.
7. **Set Up Version Control (Optional but Recommended):** If you're working in a team or want to keep track of changes to your project, setting up version control is crucial. Unity supports various version control systems like Git, SVN, and Perforce. You can integrate version control through Unity Hub or directly within Unity.
8. **Start Developing Your Game:** With Unity set up and your project initialized, you're ready to start developing your game!

5.6.2 Development and Deployment

To develop a game project in unity we have to follow these 4 main steps repeatedly to create the desired project.

There is an individual scene for every activity or page. Steps for these includes:-

1. **Create Game Assets:** Develop or acquire assets for your game, including 2D models, textures, animations, sound effects, and music. You can create assets yourself using software like Blender, Photoshop, or Audacity, or you can find ready-made assets in the Unity Asset Store or other online platforms.
2. **Design Levels and Scenes:** Plan and design your game levels and scenes using Unity's Scene view. Place **Game Objects**, set up environments, add lighting, and define the layout and flow of your game.
3. **Scripting:** Write scripts in visual studio to add functionality and behavior to your game objects. Unity uses C# as its primary scripting language, so it's essential to learn C# fundamentals. You can create scripts to control player movement, implement game mechanics, manage UI elements, and more.

4. **Implement Game Mechanics:** Translate your game design into code by implementing core gameplay mechanics. This might include player controls, enemy AI, physics interactions, collision detection, scoring systems, and game rules.

5.6.3 Creating a scene in Unity

Here's a basic outline to get you started:

1. Open Unity:

Launch the Unity Hub → open unity and create a new project or open an existing one.

2. Create a New Scene:

- In the Unity Editor, go to the **`File`** menu, then **`New Scene`** to create a new scene.
- Alternatively, you can use the shortcut **`Ctrl + N`** (Cmd + N on Mac).

3. Set up the Scene:

- Arrange your scene by adding **Game Objects**. This could include things like the main character, enemies, obstacles, environment objects, lights, cameras, etc.
- You can add **Game Objects** by right-clicking in the Hierarchy window or by using the **Game Object** menu.

4. Add Terrain or Environment:

If your game requires terrain or a specific environment, you can create or import them. Unity provides tools for terrain sculpting, painting textures, and placing objects directly onto the terrain.

5. Set up Lighting:

- Lighting is crucial for setting the mood and atmosphere of your scene.
- You can use Unity's built-in lighting system or install third-party lighting packages for more advanced effects.

6. Set up Cameras:

- Cameras determine the player's perspective in the game.

- You can adjust camera properties **such as** field of view, depth, and position to achieve the desired view for your game.

7. Add Scripts:

Attach scripts to **Game Objects** to define their behavior. For example, you might have a script that controls the player character's movement, another script for objects, and so on.

8. Test Your Scene:

Use Unity's Play mode to test your scene in action. This allows you to interact with your game and identify any issues or areas for improvement.

9. Iterate and Refine:

Game development is an iterative process. Continuously playtest your scene, gather feedback, and make adjustments to improve gameplay, performance, and aesthetics.

10. Save Your Scene:

- Once you're satisfied with your scene, save your work by going to the `File` menu and selecting `Save Scene`.
- It's also a good idea to save your entire project regularly to prevent data loss.

5.6.4 C# SCRIPT IN UNITY

In Unity, a script is a piece of code written in a programming language like C# that allows you to define the behavior of game objects and control their interactions within your Unity project.

Scripts allow you to define how game objects behave and interact with each other. **For example**, you can write a script to control the movement of a player character, handle user input, manage game mechanics like scoring or health, or trigger animations.

Scripts can respond to events that occur during gameplay, such as collisions between objects, clicks on UI elements, or changes in game state. This allows you to create dynamic and interactive experiences for players.

Unity provides a wide range of built-in components and functionality, but scripts allow you to extend and customize these features to suit the specific needs of your game. You can create custom behaviors, algorithms, and systems tailored to your game design.

Scripts can be used to integrate Unity projects with external systems and services, such as databases, networking libraries, or hardware devices. This enables features like online multiplayer, data analytics, or support for specialized input devices.

Scripts are typically attached to game objects as components, allowing you to easily control their behavior and properties directly within the Unity Editor. You can create and edit scripts using the integrated development environment (IDE) provided by Unity, and then attach them to game objects by simply dragging and dropping.

Following is an example C# code (script) of how the game transition works from one scene or main menu to another scene:-

```
using UnityEngine;
using UnityEngine.SceneManagement;

public class MainMenu : MonoBehaviour
{
    // Function to start the game
    public void StartGame()
    {
        // Load the scene with index 1 (assuming index 0 is the main menu scene)
        SceneManager.LoadScene(1);
    }
    // Function to go to options menu
    public void OpenOptions()
    {
        // Load the scene with index 2 (assuming index 2 is the options menu scene)
        SceneManager.LoadScene(2);
    }
    // Function to quit the game
    public void QuitGame()
    {
```

```
        // Exit the application
        Application.Quit();
    }
}
```

5.6.5 Loading project in computer

To load this project into the Unity Editor, follow these steps:

- 1. Open Unity Hub:** If you haven't already, download and install Unity Hub, which is a management tool for Unity projects and installations. Once installed, open Unity Hub.
- 2. Add the Project:** In Unity Hub, click on the "Projects" tab. Then, click the "Add" button and navigate to the folder where you downloaded the Unity project. Select the folder containing the Unity project, i.e. **FYP** and Unity Hub will add it to your projects list.
- 3. Open the Project:** Once the project is added, you can double-click on it in the Unity Hub projects list to open it in the Unity Editor.
- 4. Wait for Import:** When you open the project in Unity, it will begin importing assets and setting up the project. Depending on the size of the project and your computer's performance, this process may take some time.
- 5. Review:** After the import process completes, Unity may display any errors or warnings that occurred during the import. Review these errors and warnings in the Console window and resolve them as needed. Common issues may include missing assets, incompatible Unity versions, or deprecated code.
- 6. Explore and Modify:** Once the project is successfully imported, you can explore its contents in the Unity Editor. You can view scenes, inspect assets, modify scripts, and make changes to the project as desired.

7. Play the Game: If the project includes a playable game, you can test it by clicking the play button in the Unity Editor to enter Play mode.

5.6.6 To Run This Project directly into mobile:

1. Attached the mobile by USB Cable with your computer.
2. Copy the **KG-Learn.apk** in your phone.
3. Install the Apk file in your phone.
4. Play the game and learn/enjoy.

CHAPTE NO 6
CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

6.1 Conclusion

A software project means a lot of experience. Working with the game engine is the one completely new experience, we are dealing with a different language, and it is very sensitive and means a long time because the game engine is trying to connect the game with reality. Creating a 3D model game is very difficult because we have to watch each point of the model. So basically this game is developed for the entertainment and educational purpose. And the game could also be run with minimum requirement in any window 10. It provides the basic knowledge how the KG-Learn game made and what was its basic architecture. Plus the project also gives an overview of the capabilities of 3D engine.

“KG-learn” aims to provide a fun and educational experience for children, helping them develop essential math skills through interactive gameplay. By leveraging Unity and C#, we can create a high-quality, engaging, and accessible learning tool that benefits both children and parents.

6.2 Future work

Looking ahead, there are several improvements and enhancements planned for KG-Learn to make it more comprehensive and engaging:

- **Expansion of Categories:** Introduce more educational topics and levels to cover a wider range of learning areas.
- **Enhanced Graphics:** Improve the visual appeal and animation quality to create a more immersive experience.
- **New Features:** Incorporate additional functionalities such as quizzes, reward systems, and in-game helpers.
- **Upgraded Content:** Revamp existing categories with more dynamic and challenging gameplay elements.
- **Improved Comparison Tools:** Develop smarter systems to track and compare user progress more effectively.

- **Cross-Platform Compatibility:** Extend support to Android devices including smartphones, tablets, and iPad.
- **Leaderboard Integration:** Implement a weekly leaderboard where top-performing users can earn exclusive in-game rewards.

These future updates aim to further enhance the learning experience, making **KG-Learn Educational Kids Learning Game** an even more valuable tool for early childhood education.

6.3 References

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